

»CO-PHOTOGRAPHY« AS A RESEARCH TOOL – USING NARRATIVE PHOTOGRAPHY AS A PARTICIPATORY TOOL FOR USER INSIGHTS

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WORKSHOP POSITION PAPER

Background Issues

As a contribution to this year's conference theme *Colours of Care* we propose a workshop on *Co-photography* as a design research tool. The term *Co-photography* was coined by the workshop's organizers to combine participatory methods as applied in co-design processes and photography as an

empiric story-telling tool. The workshop is linked to the D&E 2014 design case paper "*Tap Anything.*" *A Design (Class) Case: Teaching Participatory Design Methods as Design Basics.* The design case reports from a participatory design process including a workshop from which the idea of *Co-photography* evolved (see Fig. 1).

We see the workshop located within the designated conference topics *Design for Social Innovation, Methodological Issues of Design and Emotion* and *Experience and Interaction.*

Figure 1. Scene from participatory workshop in a primary school. Playful and effective rating system for kids 'jury' rating prototypes using cardboard plates with smiley faces.

In this hands-on workshop participants will learn about participatory methods in general, about the potential and creative value in developing their own participatory methods and tools for user insights, and will then go out into the field and practice *Co-photography* within a one-hour brief project based on their own method design. The workshop results in a popup exhibition of the photographic results.

Co-design describes involving stakeholders and future users of products or services strongly in the design process. Expressing creativity, ideas and thoughts in words or sketches may be difficult for many people if they are not used or trained to do so. A common method to help them express themselves and to be creative is providing participatory toolkits (Sanders 2003, 2013): kits containing crafting material such as stickers, Lego blocs, fabrics, etc. as a means of assembling prototypes and sketch ideas.

Our workshop is based on Liz Sanders model of *Say, Do, Make* – listing tools and techniques that complement and reinforce each other in the participatory design process (2013). We apply this model to photography as a means of expressing oneself and tell a story. Photography in general is an excellent medium to capture emotions and information, therefore it is an essential documentary tool for later analysis in participatory workshops, observations, etc. We propose not using photography to document a participatory outcome in a co-design workshop but to let it be the outcome: materials from a toolkit provided by the researchers shall be used by the questioners for making artifacts, props, etc. to ‘stage’ their photographic answer (see Fig. 2). The outcome could be described as a visual short story (see ‘Narrative Photography,’ e.g. Black Box Gallery 2011).

This technique draws from the concept of design probes (Gaver 1999), in which it is not the researcher who takes photos as a tool for insight, as known from the visual data collection in ethnographic photography and visual anthropology (e.g. Theye 1989, Levi-Strauss 1978, Sander 1929), but the future user/questioner who is asked to take a photo as a visual answer to a question.

Workshop Goal

Attendees get an overview of participatory approaches and methods and learn that methods can be varied, changed,

adapted – they can themselves be designed. They make their own hands-on experiences with photography as a participatory method, preparing interviews, approaching questioners, collecting data, etc. Analysis of the data will be brushed but not executed in depth. The workshop is meant to enhance the vocabulary of design researchers that already use participatory methods but have not yet included photography to their palette, as well as designers and researchers that are entirely unfamiliar with the co-design method and would like to practice it for the first time in a playful environment.

Approach

Part 1 (30 minutes): brief keynote presentations by the organizers on the use of participatory methods and applications in the design context as well as a brief introduction to narrative photography

Part 2 (30 minutes): pressure project. Design brief, brainstorming, developing individual method, paper prototyping, fieldwork preparation

Part 3 (60 minutes): fieldwork/practice *Co-photography*. Attendees swarm out and get people to take photos as answers to prepared simple but playful questions (e.g., ‘How are you today?’, ‘How was your lunch today?’ and also more complex questions like ‘What is your relationship to your neighbors?’, ‘What is your relationship to politics?’, etc.)

Part 4 (60 minutes): sighting and selection of images, open discussion, résumé

Part 5 (post-workshop, optional): printing out photos on site on a mobile printer provided by the workshop’s organizers for putting together a pop-up exhibition of workshop results (photos) at the D&E conference

NAMES, AFFILIATIONS, AND CONTACT INFORMATION OF THE ORGANIZERS:

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Fig. 2: Based on Sanders (2013) model of *Say, Do and Make* – tools and techniques that complement and reinforce each other in the participatory design process. Model showing *Co-photography* involving all dimensions of a participatory design toolkit

Intended Number of Attendees: Minimum: 12, maximum: 25

Planned Length of the Workshop: Half a day workshop (3 hours)

Preferred City for the Workshop: Bogotá

Characteristics of the Space/room Needed to Conduct the Workshop:

Workshop room with tables and chairs for max. 25 participants, projector, flipchart.

Optional: exhibition space during the conference. A designated wall or small room, ideally in a waiting/resting area. If no wall is available, partition walls or similar.

Materials needed by attendees: digital camera, if on hand: laptop.

Basic materials for toolkits are provided by workshop organizers. Attendees are encouraged to contribute by bringing whatever material they have at hand.

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Annelie Franke is a designer and photographer born in 1976 in Lauchhammer, Germany. Between 1997 and 2001 she studied Communication Design at the Rhein Main University in Wiesbaden (Germany). From 2001 to 2004 she studied Visual Communication at the University of the Arts Berlin (UdK).

She has received design and photography awards and worked as a designer with various agencies and educational institutions in Berlin, Weimar, Schwerin and Wiesbaden. In 2006 she followed her heart to Bogotá and began working as a professor at the Universidad de los Andes in the Department of Architecture and Design. Her emphases are digital studio photography, experimental typography, conceptual and information design. Besides, she works as freelance designer and photographer in various projects in both countries. Her artistic work stresses the importance of small things in life. Using various media such as photography, illustration and design, she exalts unnoticed and common things of everyday life to turn them into main actors of her work, and ennobles evident ugliness to natural beauty.

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Monika Hoinkis, born 1978 in Hanover, Germany is a Berlin-based designer and design educator. She studied visual communication and time based art in Berlin and Sydney, Australia, graduating from University of the Arts Berlin (UdK). Currently she holds a professorship for processual design at University of Applied Sciences in Potsdam. When she finds the time Monika also works on private art and design projects as well as design commissions as a freelance designer. Her work was internationally exhibited and received diverse awards (iF, tdc, ADC, reddot). Her particular interest lies in the social and societal impacts and implications of design.

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